

3D-shaped binders of unfolded proteins inducing cancer cell specific endoplasmic reticulum stress *in vitro* and *in vivo*

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Abstract

Unfolded protein response is upregulated in cancer cells leading to the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) stress. Therefore, cancer cells are sensitive to drugs capable of further enhancing the ER stress. Examples of such drugs include clinically approved proteasome inhibitors bortezomib and carfilzomib. Unfortunately, the known ER stress inducers exhibit dose limiting side effects that justifies search for better, more cancer specific drugs of this type. Herein we report on clathrochelate 2, which binds to unfolded proteins, prevents their further processing thereby leading to the ER stress and ROS increase in cancer, but not normal cells. Due to the cancer specific mode of action, 2 is not toxic *in vivo* up to the dose of 147 mg/kg, does not affect normal blood and bone marrow cells at the therapeutically active dose, but strongly suppresses both primary tumor growth (confirmed in 3 models of murine tumor) and spreading of metastases (LLC1 lung cancer model).

Introduction

Chemotherapy is an established method of cancer treatment. It explores different sensitivity of cancer and normal cells to some chemotherapeutic agents. For example, drugs binding to DNA (Pt^{2+} complexes, alkylating agents, intercalators) or to DNA-binding proteins (camptothecin and its derivatives affecting topoisomerase I) and drugs inducing DNA modification (antimetabolites) all disturb replication and transcription thereby affecting rapidly dividing cancer cells stronger than normal cells.¹ Another prominent feature of many types of cancer cells is the upregulated unfolded protein response (UPR) caused by the accumulation of unfolded proteins (UPs) and leading to the elevated endoplasmic reticulum (ER) stress (Figure 1A).²

Figure 1. **A.** Illustration of a hallmark of cancer cells: a higher concentration of unfolded proteins (UPs) and enhanced ER stress. **B.** An approach to selectively kill cancer cells by inducing the ER stress by a binder of UPs (BUP). The critical level of the ER stress is indicated with a red line. **C.** Structures of FeCs 1-5 and C₆₀.²¹

The already stressed cancer cells are highly responsive to drugs able to further amplify the ER stress that has been explored in the cancer therapy. In particular, proteasome inhibitors bortezomib³ and carfilzomib⁴ have been approved both in the USA and EU for the treatment of multiple myeloma. Unfortunately, these drugs are not fully cell specific. They affect normal cells leading to dose-limiting neutropenia and thrombocytopenia, gastro-intestinal effects and peripheral neuropathy^{3,4} that justifies the search for the less toxic drugs.

Metallo drugs are emerging as alternative ER stress-inducers.^{2b,5} Compared to organic drugs, they offer additional metal-centered reactivity for drug design including coordination chemistry, photo(redox)chemistry and dark redox chemistry. The metallo drugs can trigger the ER stress via four distinct upstream events. First, coordinatively unsaturated complexes (CUCs) form metal - biomolecule bonds: e.g., Pt^{2+} in cisplatin binds N7 of purine residues in DNA,⁶ Au^+ complexes coordinate a selenocysteine residue in thioredoxin reductase,⁷ Ir^{3+} half-sandwich complexes bind histidine and cysteine residues in proteins⁸ and a Ru^{3+} complex BOLD-100/KP1339 binds ribosomal proteins.⁹ Second, redox active complexes induce generation of reactive products via electron transfer to intracellular substrates, e.g., polypyridyl complexes

of Ru²⁺ and aminoferrocene drugs^{10,11} catalyze generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) O₂^{•-} and HO• from O₂ and H₂O₂. Third, metal complexes induce generation of toxic products via photoinduced energy or electron transfers, e.g., VO²⁺, bimetallic Cu⁺-Fe²⁺ and Ir³⁺ complexes¹²⁻¹⁴ all act as photosensitizers by generating ROS including either ¹O₂ or O₂^{•-} or both of them. Fourth, positively charged lipophilic compounds, e.g., cyclometallated Ir³⁺ complexes¹⁵, are accumulated in the negatively charged membrane of mitochondria (Mit) causing Mit dysfunction and ROS production. In all four cases either coordination of CUCs to nucleophilic sites of biological macromolecules or intracellular ROS generation or both of these take place not only in cancer, but also in normal cells that leads to undesired toxicity.

In search of alternative ER stress inducers, which are not CUCs and cannot catalyze systemic ROS production, our attention was drawn to binders of unfolded proteins (BUPs). These could stabilize UPs, eventually leading to their accumulation or/and aggregation thereby inducing the ER stress (Figures 1B). The interaction of BUP and UPs is at least a bimolecular reaction. As such it is strongly dependent from concentrations of both BUP and UPs. In cancer cells containing the high level of UPs, the equilibrium BUP + UPs → BUP/UPs is shifted to BUP/UPs leading to the ER stress. In contrast, in normal cells containing the low level of UPs, this equilibrium is shifted towards the unbound UPs, which can be normally processed. Thus, the optimized BUP will be toxic to cancer cells, but not affect normal cells (Figure 1B), thereby solving the problem of side effects of common ER stress inducers.³⁻¹⁵

Several synthetic binders of UPs have been identified previously, e.g., chemical chaperones 4-phenylbutyrate and lysophosphatidic acids¹⁶ as well as a molecular tweezer CLR01.¹⁷ In contrast to the suggested BUPs, they reduce the intracellular load of UPs thereby attenuating rather than enhancing the ER stress.¹⁸ Correspondingly, anticancer activity of these compounds is low.¹⁹ Another potential BUP is carbon allotrope fullerene C₆₀. Though it is known to bind strongly UPs,²⁰ medicinal applications of C₆₀ are limited by its poor solubility in water (logS= -11.0²¹). A better water soluble metal-containing carbon allotrope Gd-C₈₂(OH)₂₂ exhibits moderate anticancer activity.²² However, its mode of action is not related to binding UPs. We have previously prepared and studied Fe-clathrochelates (FeCs), which are coordination compounds with a 3D-shaped structure having dimensions similar to that of C₆₀ (Figure 1C).²³ We have found that, similarly to C₆₀, the FeCs functionalized with either six (Vz375, Scheme S1, supporting information, S1²⁴) or two carboxylic acid moieties (FeC **1**,²⁵ Figure 1C) bind to model UPs. Their anticancer activity has not been studied before. Compared to C₆₀, the FeCs exhibit several favorable properties. In particular, as less hydrophobic compounds the FeCs are more water soluble (e.g., logS= -4.4 for FeC **2**, Figure 1C). Furthermore, in contrast to C₆₀, they are not redox active at physiological conditions and, therefore, not expected to directly generate ROS or other toxic reactive species that could adversely affect normal cells. Importantly, chemical modification of the exterior of FeCs is straightforward and can be achieved by the variation of the substituents of the dioxime ligands and boron-containing cap groups that allows fine tuning of the properties of FeCs for medicinal applications.²³ All factors mentioned above make FeCs a suitable scaffold for the development of the BUPs. A single previously reported FeCs exhibiting some anticancer activity is electrophilic FeC-Cl₆ (Scheme S1, S1).²⁶ The latter compound alkylates intracellular glutathione (GSH) leading to the ROS increase in both cancer and normal cells and, therefore, is not suitable for further development as a drug.

In this paper, we report on the optimized BUP FeC **2**. It binds model UPs, induces the accumulation of immature proteins and the ER stress as well as the increase of levels of

mitochondrial ROS and nitric oxide (NO) in cancer cells. In contrast, it does not affect normal cells. Further, the FeC is practically nontoxic in vivo and exhibits the strong anticancer and antimetastatic activity in three murine models of cancer.

Results and Discussion

Preliminary studies, synthesis and properties of the selected FeCs in cell free settings

Though previously reported Vz375²⁴ and **1**²⁵ bind UPs, they are either inactive (Vz375, half-maximal inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) > 50 μM for human ovarian carcinoma A2780 cells) or exhibit weak anticancer activity towards a range of cancer cell lines: IC₅₀ values of **1** for human acute promyelocytic leukemia HL-60, A2780, Burkitt's lymphoma BL-2, T-cells leukemia Jurkat and lung cancer SK-MES-1 cells are >32 μM, whereas the IC₅₀ for murine lung cancer LLC1 cells is >15 μM (Table 1).

Table 1. Effects of FeCs on the viability of selected cancer cell lines^a.

FeC	Half-maximal inhibitory concentration (IC ₅₀) for cell lines					
	HL-60	A2780	BL-2	Jurkat	SK-MES1	LLC1
1	40 ± 2	40 ± 1	32 ± 5	>50 ^b	43 ± 3	>15 ^c
2	1.3 ± 0.3	2.6 ± 0.6	0.6 ± 0.1	3 ± 1 ^b	21 ± 2	12.0 ± 0.4 ^c
4	-	2.9 ± 0.2	-	-	-	-
5	-	4.7 ± 0.0	-	-	-	-

^a The cells were incubated with the compounds for 48 h, except of data indicated with ^b (24 h) and ^c (72 h). FeC= clathrochelate.

Since these FeCs are relatively polar due to the presence of six (Vz375) or two (**1**) carboxylic acid groups, their low activity could be caused by the inefficient membrane permeability. To find out whether this is the case, we investigated the uptake of one of these compounds by BL-2 cells. By using atomic emission spectroscopy we observed no statistically significant increase of the intracellular amount of both iron and boron in BL-2 cells incubated for 4 h with **1** (9 μM) as compared to untreated BL-2 cells (Figure 2A). These data confirm that the uptake of FeC **1** by BL-2 cells is poor.

In search for membrane permeable FeCs, we explored potentially more lipophilic FeCs containing one (**2**) or no carboxylic acids (**3**²⁷) (Figure 1C). The previously unknown FeC **2** was prepared starting from electrophilic FeC intermediate **S1** by the nucleophilic substitution reaction using thiophenol in the presence of triethylamine (NEt₃) as described the *SI*. To evaluate lipophilicity of FeCs **2** and **3**, we determined their *n*-octanol/water partition coefficients (logP's, Table S1, *SI*). As expected, both compounds (logP(**2**)= 4.6 ± 0.2, logP(**3**)= 5.6 ± 0.3) are more lipophilic than the reference FeC **1** (logP= 3.7 ± 0.1). Importantly, despite its higher lipophilicity, solubility of FeCs **2** in aqueous solutions is still sufficient for the studies of its biological activity: 40 ± 8 μM in aqueous phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) solution and 74 ± 10 μM in Roswell Park Memorial Institute 1640 (RPMI 1640) medium containing 5% fetal bovine serum (FBS), 1% L-glutamine (Gln), 1% Penicillin/Streptomycin (Table S2, *SI*). In contrast, FeC **3** is insoluble at >10 μM in the aqueous solutions that precluded its further tests. All further studies were focused on FeC **2** and its analogues **4** and **5**.

Anticancer effects, the active form of FeC **2**

The reference FeC **1** is weakly toxic towards several human and murine cancer cell lines

originating from blood (HL-60, BL-2, Jurkat), ovary (A2780) and lungs (SK-MES1, LLC1). We tested the effects of FeC **2** on the same set of cells to be able to compare anticancer efficacies of **2** and reference **1**. We found that FeC **2** is a substantially more potent anticancer agent than **1**, affecting cell viability at the IC₅₀ ranging from 0.6 μM for most sensitive BL-2 cells to 21 μM for least sensitive SK-MES1 cells (Table 1). These data clearly show that the presence of one (**2**) rather than two (**1**) or six (Vz375) CO₂H groups is required for the anticancer activity of the clathrochelates. We conducted further *in vitro* studies mostly with A2780 cells as a representative cancer cell line. In few cases the same experiments were also done for BL-2 cells to confirm that the effects observed are not restricted to a single cell line.

To find out whether it is critical for the activity that the CO₂H group is directly attached to the phenyl ring, we prepared an analogue FeC **4** containing a methylene bridge between the phenyl ring and the CO₂H group. This compound was obtained in two steps (*SI*). First, the nucleophilic substitution reaction between electrophilic intermediate **S2** and 2-(4-mercaptothienyl)acetic acid in the presence of NEt₃ furnished intermediate **S3**. Second, **S3** was reacted with thiophenol in the presence of NEt₃ to obtain FeC **4**. We found that anticancer efficacy of FeC **4** in A2780 cells (IC₅₀= 2.6 ± 0.6 μM) is identical to that of FeC **2** (IC₅₀= 2.9 ± 0.2 μM, Student's t-test, p > 0.05). These data might indicate that the binding site of **2** and **4** in their putative target can tolerate at least small structural changes that would be in agreement with binding to unstructured UPs. The latter conclusion is further supported by the fact that FeC **5**, containing a larger propargylaminocarbonyl moiety in the para-position of one of the phenyl residues is only slightly less active than its analogue **2**: IC₅₀= 4.7 ± 0.0 μM *versus* 2.6 ± 0.6 μM, correspondingly (Table 1). We prepared FeC **5** for the study of the intracellular distribution of FeCs as described below.

Lipophilic drugs can form aggregates in aqueous solutions, which may destabilize protein structure leading to their unfolding thereby causing both cell and target unspecific toxicity.²⁸ To exclude this possibility, we investigated whether FeC **2** forms aggregates by using UV-visible spectroscopy and dynamic light scattering (DLS). We observed that absorbance at 487 nm (A_{max}) of solutions of **2** in aqueous PBS (pH 7.4) is linearly dependent from the compound concentration up to at least 30 μM (R²= 0.9986, Figure S10, *SI*) indicating that only one species exists in this concentration range. Further, we did not detect aggregated species in aqueous solutions of FeC **2** at < 30 μM by using DLS. These data indicate that **2** exists in the monomeric form in aqueous solutions at < 30 μM concentrations. Since IC₅₀ values for the tested cancer cell lines are also < 30 μM (Table 1), we conclude that the monomeric form rather than the aggregates is responsible for the anticancer activity of the FeC.

A single previously described clathrochelate exhibiting strong anticancer activity is an electrophilic derivative FeC_{Cl6} (Scheme S1, *SI*). Its mode of action relies on the covalent modification of GSH via the nucleophilic substitution of the chlorides in the FeC.²⁶ Potentially, FeC **2** could exhibit the similar chemical reactivity via the substitution of a PhS⁻ moiety with GS⁻ derived from GSH. It is a less likely reaction, because the PhS⁻ is not as good leaving group as the Cl⁻. However, in cancer cells the latter reaction can be facilitated by the follow-up oxidation of the PhS⁻ to PhSSPh thereby shifting the equilibrium towards the product. By using LC-MS (Figure S11, *SI*) as well as by monitoring the release of free Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺ ions (Table S3, *SI*), we confirmed that FeC **2** is chemically stable both in the absence and presence of GSH. We also found that this compound is stable under other conditions, which it could encounter in cancer cells: pH 7.4 (cytoplasm), pH 5 (lysosome), in the presence of H₂O₂ (ER) (Figure S11, Table S3, *SI*). The high stability of the FeC is also retained in cells. In particular, we analyzed the extract of A2780 cells incubated with this compound (3 μM) for 1 and 24 h by

using LC-MS (Figures S12-S14, *SI*). We detected only the parent compound after 1 h incubation, whereas at the longer incubation time (24 h) we additionally detected metabolite **2a** (educt of **2** with GSH), which was formed with 10 % yield. As it is discussed below, the biological effects, including the induction of the ER stress, occur already after 10 min of the incubation of **2** with cells. Therefore, the metabolite **2a** formed much later is not expected to play a critical role in the activity of **2**. These data confirm that **2** acts via the different mechanism than the previously reported FeC₂Cl₆.²⁶

Uptake mechanism, intracellular distribution and effects of FeC 2 on intracellular organelles

In contrast to FeC **1**, the uptake of FeC **2** (9 μ M, 4 h incubation) by BL-2 and A2780 cells is high at 37 °C (Figure 2A). That explains why **2** is a more potent anticancer agent than **1**, despite their similar affinity to UPs. The uptake of **2** is strongly inhibited at 5 °C (Student's t test, $p < 0.01$, Figures 2A, S15-S17, *SI*). The latter data indicate that the cellular transport of the FeC requires energy and, therefore, occurs via the active mechanism or mechanisms. We identified these to be clathrin- and caveolin-mediated endocytosis, since the chlorpromazine (CPZ) and genistein (GNS), which are inhibitors of these biochemical processes, suppress the uptake of **2** significantly ($p < 0.01$, Figure 2B, S19, *SI*). The inhibitor of organic anion transporters (OATs) bromosulphthalein (BSP) does not suppress the uptake indicating that OATs are not involved in the transport of **2** (Figure 2B).

To evaluate the intracellular distribution of FeC **2**, we prepared its analogue containing a terminal alkyne moiety – FeC **5**, whose synthesis was described elsewhere.²⁹ Incubation of A2780 cells with FeC **5** (9 μ M) for 0.5, 2 and 4 h, followed by their fixation, treatment with either Alexa Fluor® 488 azide or Alexa Fluor® 594 azide under the conditions of Cu⁺-catalyzed alkyne-azide cycloaddition “click” reaction, washing and monitoring the signal of the Alexa Fluor® dyes allowed visualization of the transport of the FeC (Figure 2C-E). We found that the fluorescence signal observed in A2780 cells treated with FeC **5** can be suppressed by the co-incubation of **5** with the unlabeled **2** indicating that both **5** and **2** bind to the same intracellular target or targets (Figure S20, *SI*). After the incubation for 30 min the FeC is located in the cellular periphery, which can be the cellular membrane and/or the FeC bound to the components of the active transport associated with the membrane (Figures 2C, S21, *SI*). At the longer incubation time (2h), the FeC is located in the proximity of the nucleus that can be either ER or Golgi or both (Figures 2D, S21, *SI*). At the longest incubation time (4h), the FeC is distributed evenly within the cell. For example, the signal is partially co-localized with the nuclear stain (Pearson's coefficient 0.55, Figures 2E, S21, *SI*).

Within cells UPs are formed, processed and eventually accumulated mostly in the ER and lysosomes (LYs). Correspondingly, if FeC **2** induces the accumulation of UPs (Figure 1B), one of these organelles or both of them might be stressed. We observed that after only 10 min incubation with FeC **2** the fluorescence of A2780 cells, stained with the ER specific dye ER-tracker™ Green for additional 20 min, is significantly reduced ($p < 0.01$) indicating that the ER is affected by **2**. The effect is saturated after 30 min incubation (Figure 2F). In contrast, FeC **2** (up to 24 h incubation) does not change the fluorescence of the cells labelled with LY– specific dye acridine orange (Figures S22, S23, *SI*) that excludes LYs as the primary target of the FeC. Interestingly, treatment of the cells labelled with Mit-specific dye rhodamine 123 (R123) with FeC **2** for 4 and 24 h also leads to the strong decrease of the R123 fluorescence indicating that the FeC affects the Mit (Figures S22, S23, *SI*). The latter effect is secondary to that on the ER, since it appears at the substantially longer incubation time.

Figure 2. **A.** Uptake of FeCs **1** and **2** (each 9 μ M, incubation: 4h) in BL-2 cells at 37 $^{\circ}$ C or 5 $^{\circ}$ C by monitoring intracellular iron content (*S/I*). Inset: a photo of BL-2 cells incubated with the FeC or controls (yellow colour indicates accumulation of FeCs): (1) DMSO, 37 $^{\circ}$ C; (2) FeC **1**, 37 $^{\circ}$ C; (3) FeC **2**, 37 $^{\circ}$ C; (4) DMSO, 5 $^{\circ}$ C; (5) FeC **2**, 5 $^{\circ}$ C. **B.** Cells were pre-treated with the organic anion transporter inhibitor bromosulphthalein (BSP, 500 μ M, 5 min pre-incubation), with clathrin-mediated uptake inhibitor chlorpromazine (CPZ, 10 μ g/mL, 2 h pre-incubation) or with caveolin-mediated uptake inhibitor genistein (GNS, 400 μ M). After the pre-incubation, the cells were treated with FeC **2** for 2 h in the medium at 37 $^{\circ}$ C. The uptake was evaluated by determination of intracellular iron amount. **C-E.** Visualization of the intracellular distribution of FeC **5** (9 μ M) in A2780 cells after 0.5 h, 2 h and 4 h incubation. The FeC was labelled by Alexa Fluor[®] 594 Azide. The nuclei of the cells were co-stained with Hoechst 33342. Ch1 (red) - λ_{ex} : 561 nm; λ_{em} : 595/50 nm; Ch2 (blue) - λ_{ex} : 355 nm; λ_{em} : 450/50 nm. **F.** Effects of the time of FeC **2** (9 μ M) incubation with A2780 cells (10 min – 2 h) on ER-specific staining of the cells. After the cells were incubated with the FeC for the specified time, the ER-probe was added and the cells were incubated for additional 20 min (*S/I*). For **A**, **B**, **F**: An unpaired Student's t-test *: $p < 0.05$; **: $p < 0.01$; ***: $p < 0.001$; ns ≥ 0.05 . **G**, **H.** Transmission electron microscopic (TEM) images of A2780 cells. **G**: control (no FeC added). **H**: FeC **2** (9 μ M), pre-incubation for 10 min. Arrows indicate ER, arrow heads indicate mitochondria.

In particular, the effect on the ER is saturated after 30 min incubation, whereas that on Mit is not saturated even after 4 h incubation (Figure S24). By using JC-1, a dye sensitive to Mit membrane potential (MMP), we found that the FeC induces the decrease of MMP (Figures S25, S26, *S/I*).

Next, we determined whether the FeC is physically accumulated in particular organelles or the observed effects are indirect. These experiments required large cell numbers (5×10^7 cells) due to the technical limitations of the analytical method (AES) applied for monitoring Fe and B derived from the FeC in organelles (*S/I*). We used BL-2 rather than A2780 cells, since the former cells can be easily obtained in large quantities. We analyzed the content of ER, Mit and

LYs from the cells, which were pre-incubated with FeC **2** (9 μ M) for 1 h, and found that only ER and Mit, but not LYs fractions contain FeC **2** (Figures S27A, C, F). These data indicate that the FeC is directly accumulated in the ER and Mit.

By using transmission electron microscopy (TEM, Figure 2G, H, more detailed images are provided in Figure S28, *SI*), we visualized morphological changes of the intracellular organelles in response to the FeC treatment. We found that the FeC causes the increase of volume of the ER (arrows in Figures 2G, H) and changes the morphology of Mit (triangles).

Thus, according to the described in this section data, we could identify the ER as a primary target of FeC **2**.

The mechanism of anticancer activity of FeC 2

Studies in cell free settings

We considered two possible modes of action of FeC **2**, which could cause the effect on the ER leading to the anticancer activity. First, this FeC can first bind UPs, inhibiting their maturation or inducing aggregation thereby causing the ER stress. This possibility is based on the fact that the previously described analogues of **2**, clathrochelates Vz375²⁴ and **1**²⁵ are binders of UPs in cell free settings. Second, FeC **2** is a complex of Fe²⁺. Therefore, it can potentially induce generation of highly toxic species O₂⁻ and HO[•] by donating an electron from the metal ion to less toxic O₂ and H₂O₂ thereby inducing the oxidative stress in the ER and disturbing its function. It has been previously reported that ROS-inducers can cause the ER stress leading to cancer cell death.^{10,11} In this section the experiments will be described, which allowed us confirming one of these possibilities.

To evaluate whether FeC **2** binds to UPs, we selected unfolded bovine serum albumin (further uBSA) as a representative protein. uBSA was obtained by incubation of BSA with a dithiothreitol (DTT, 1 mM) at 45 °C. We confirmed formation of uBSA under these conditions by using thioflavin T probe (ThT, 10 μ M), whose fluorescence is increased in the presence of unfolded and aggregated proteins (Figures 3A, S29, *SI*).

Figure 3. **A.** Dependence of fluorescence of thioflavin T (ThT, 10 μ M, $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 440$ nm; $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 480 \pm 10$ nm) from the concentration of FeC **2** in the absence (orange curve) and presence of BSA (0.5 mg/mL). Other conditions: incubation time - 100 min, temperature 45 °C, DTT (1 mM), DMSO (1% (v/v)). **B.** Kinetics of BSA (0.5 mg/mL) aggregation monitored by dynamic light

scattering (DLS) under conditions of (A), except that T was not added. [FeC 2]= 9 μ M. DLS. The measurement at timepoint 0 min was performed before DTT addition. The size of the main peak was plotted against the incubation period. C-E. AFM images (upper plots) and height profiles along traces labelled with "I" (lower plots). Samples: C - buffer (PBS (10 mM, 150 mM NaCl, pH = 7.4), BSA (0.5 mg/mL) with either DMSO (1 %, v/v, D) or FeC 2 (9 μ M) and DMSO (E). Other conditions: T= 45 °C, incubation time < 5 min, [DTT]= 1 mM.

We observed that upon the addition of FeC 2 (3-18 μ M) to the solution containing uBSA and ThT the intensity of the characteristic for uBSA/ThT fluorescence is decreased in a dose-dependent fashion. Under similar conditions but in the absence of uBSA the FeC does not affect the fluorescence of ThT (Figure 3A). These data indicate that the FeC binds to the associate uBSA/ThT. To investigate the kinetics of the process of uBSA aggregation in the presence of FeC 2 and to determine the size of the aggregates formed, we used DLS. In particular, we observed that the aggregates with the size of 110 ± 4 nm are obtained within 10 min after mixing BSA (0.5 mg/mL) and FeC 2 (9 μ M). In contrast, the aggregates grow substantially slowly ($t_{1/2} \sim 120$ min) in the absence of the FeC (Figures 3B, S30, SI). We monitored the latter reaction also by using atomic force microscopy (AFM). In control mixtures containing either buffer and DTT or buffer, DTT and BSA (leading to uBSA) no or < 10 nm (in height) nanoparticles were detected respectively (Figure 3C, D). In contrast, in the mixture of buffer, DTT, BSA and FeC 2 nanoparticles of up to 60 nm in height were detected (Figure 3E). In all cases the incubation time before the measurement was < 5 min. We conducted the latter experiment also with unfolded insulin (uINS, Figure S31, SI). uINS forms fibrils rather than nanoparticles. We observed that in the presence of the FeC more fibrils were formed. Moreover, the fibrils thickness was larger in the presence than in the absence of the FeC. Thus, the effect of FeC 2 on UPs is not restricted to one particular protein, but can be its more general property, which applies to other proteins. Next, we investigated whether FeC 2 can induce generation of highly reactive O₂^{•-} and HO[•] from less toxic O₂ and H₂O₂ in cell free settings under the conditions resembling the intracellular medium: aqueous buffer, pH 7.4, GSH 5 mM. In this experiment we used a non-fluorescent probe 2',7'-dichlorodihydrofluorescein (DCFH), which is oxidized to fluorescent 2',7'-dichlorofluorescein (DCF) in the presence of O₂^{•-} and HO[•], but not O₂ and H₂O₂ (Figure S32, SI). We observed that FeC 2 does not accelerate the oxidation of DCFH at all. The reason for this behavior is its high redox potential >1 V versus Ag/AgCl reference electrode as determined by cyclic voltamperometry (CV, Figure S33, SI).

Cellular assays

To get an overview over the signaling pathways that are affected by Fe 2, we evaluated its effects on gene expression in A2780 cells by using next generation sequencing (RNA-Seq). We determined ratios of amounts of RNAs derived from known genes in the untreated and treated groups (FeC 2: 2 μ M, 24 h incubation) and defined these parameters as FoldChange. We selected the genes fulfilling the condition of \log_2 FoldChange < -2 and > 2 for further analysis (Figure S34, SI). Based on the obtained data set and by using Ingenuity Pathway Analysis (IPA), we identified nine top scored canonical pathways induced or suppressed by the FeC (IPA, Figure 4A). In agreement with the previous experiments (Figure 2), two of these pathways are related to the ER stress: UPR and Protein Ubiquitination Pathway. The detailed effect of FeC 2 on expression of genes belonging to these pathways is outlined in Figures S35A and B, SI. We validated the latter result in the following four groups of independent experiments. First,

we confirmed the overexpression of C/EBP homologous protein (CHOP) mRNA in A2780 cells treated with FeC 2 by using PCR (Figure 4B). CHOP(GADD153) is a transcription factor,

Figure 4. Impact of FeC 2 (2 μM, 1% DMSO, 24 h) on the transcriptome of A2780 cancer cells. **A**. Most significantly altered canonical pathways. CC and CP are abbreviations for cell cycle and checkpoint, respectively. **B**. Validation of the RNAseq experiment by determination of relative gene expression of the selected genes in presence of 2 μM or 3 μM FeC 2 by using PCR. The data were normalized to GAPDH mRNA levels. (N = 3, error bars indicate standard deviations).

known to be activated under the ER stress.² Second, we observed that the level of ubiquitinated proteins is increased in the treated A2780 cells (Figure 5A). The latter data

Figure 5. A. Protein ubiquitination in A2780 cells upon treatment with DMSO (2); FeC 2 (9 μM, 30 min incubation) (3); as (2) except of 4 h incubation (4); upon treatment with bertezomib

(500 nM), 4 h incubation (5); control 1 (30 μ M), 4 h incubation (6) as detected by western blotting using a ubiquitin (E412J) rabbit mAb and an α rabbit AlexaFluor488 secondary antibody. Fluorescence imaging was performed with a iBright FL1000 λ_{ex} =455–485 nm, λ_{em} =510–555. B. Kinetics of ER stress induction in A2780 cells after incubation for 10 min - 4 h with FeC 2 (9 μ M) and subsequent determination of relative sXBP1 concentrations by qPCR using RPLP0 as a housekeeping gene. C. Fluorescence of MitoSOX™ - loaded A2780 and SBLF9 cells incubated either with DMSO (1 %, v/v) or FeC 2 (9 μ M, incubation time 2h) determined by fluorescence microscopy. D. Effects of FeC 2 on the cell cycle of A2780 cells: incubation time 24 h. E. Effects of FeC 2 (9 μ M, incubation time 4 h) on the de novo synthesis of DNA as determined by using deoxyethynyluridine treatment (2 mM, 2 h) and subsequent reaction of all DNA-incorporated alkyne groups with a Alexa Fluor® 594 azide. Red channel Ch1: λ_{ex} = 545/25 nm; λ_{em} = 605/70 nm. Blue channel, Ch2: λ_{ex} = 365 nm; λ_{em} = 445/50 nm. F. A2780 cells were treated with either DMSO (1%, v/v) or FeC 2 (3 μ M, 1% DMSO) for 24 h followed by fixation and staining with phalloidin-Atto655 (red signal, λ_{ex} = 640/30 nm; λ_{em} = 690/50 nm) and Hoechst 33342 (blue signal, λ_{ex} = 365 nm; λ_{em} = 445/50 nm). An unpaired Student's t-test was performed for statistical analysis (*: $p < 0.05$; **: $p < 0.01$; ***: $p < 0.001$).

indicated that the treatment with the FeC leads to the amplification of UPs prepared for removal via the ER-associated protein degradation (ERAD) system including the ubiquitin-proteasome pathway.² Third, we detected the formation of the elevated amount of spliced XBP1 (sXBP1)-mRNA transcript already 10 min after the treatment of A2780 cells with FeC 2 (Figure 5B, S37, S1). These data indicate the activation of inositol requiring enzyme 1 IRE1, which drives one of the pathways of the UPR.^{2a} Fourth, we observed the upregulation of the antioxidant intracellular system controlled by nuclear factor erythroid-2 related factor 2 (NRF2). This was evident from the enhanced expression of NRF2 target genes glutamate-cysteine ligase regulatory protein (GCLM) and glutamate-cysteine ligase catalytic subunit (GCLC)³⁰ (Figure 4B).

Further, we observed that in A2780 cells treated with FeC 2 the levels of mitochondrial ROS (mROS) (Figures 5C, S38, S39, S1) and NO are increased in a dose and incubation time dependent ways (Figure S40, S1). mROS ($O_2^{\cdot-}$) and NO can combine in cells with formation of highly reactive peroxynitrite anion ($ONOO^{\cdot-}$).³¹ The latter chemical species induce the strong oxidative stress in the cancer cells that should be the cause of the activation of the NRF2 system. Potentially, ROS can be produced either indirectly as a consequence of the ER stress³² or directly by donation of an electron from FeC 2 to O_2 and H_2O_2 . We excluded the latter possibility based on two experiments. First, we confirmed that the redox potential of FeC 2 is too high to act as a catalyst in ROS generation (Figures S32, S33, S1). Second, we observed that FeC 2 does not induce production of total ROS (tROS) in A2780 cells, which is detected using 5-(and-6)-chloromethyl-2',7'-dichlorodihydrofluorescein diacetate (CMDCFH-DA) as a probe (Figure S41, S1). In contrast, known iron-containing compounds capable of the direct ROS generation in cell free settings and in cells, e.g. aminoferrocene-based prodrugs, usually increase the level of intracellular tROS.^{11,33,34}

Importantly, we found that FeC 2 does not affect representative normal cells SBLF9 as established in three selected assays. In particular, we observed that FeC 2 (9 μ M) does not increase intracellular levels of mROS, NO and spliced XBP1 in SBLF9 cells at 1 h incubation time (Figures 5C, S37, S39, S40B, S1). In contrast, under the same conditions, mROS, NO and spliced XBP1 are significantly upregulated in cancer A2780 cells. The cancer specificity of FeC 2 is in agreement with the introduced above concept of BUPs (Figure 1B). In particular,

these are expected to be operative only in the presence of elevated levels of UPs found in cancer cells, but not in the presence of lower UPs levels found in normal cells.

A known effect of the ER stress is the growth arrest in G1 phase of the cell cycle³⁵ as well as inhibition of expression of many related to this process genes.³⁶ In agreement with this expectation, we observed that seven of nine top-scored pathways affected by the FeC in A2780 cells, as identified by RNA-Seq, are related to cell cycle, DNA and RNA synthesis (Figure 4A). We validated this result by the following two experiments. First, we observed that the cell cycle arrest in G1 phase is induced upon treatment of A2780 cells with FeC **2** (Figures 5D). Second, we found that the FeC inhibits *de novo* synthesis of DNA (Figure 5E, *SI*) and RNA (Figure S42, *SI*) in A2780 cells. Furthermore, Rho Guanine Nucleotide Exchange Factor 39 (ARHGEF39) is downregulated by FeC **2** according to RNA-Seq and PCR (Figure 2). ARHGEF39 protein is known to promote cell proliferation.³⁷ All these data (G1 phase cell cycle arrest, inhibition of DNA and RNA synthesis as well as the effect on ARHGEF39 contribute to antiproliferative properties of the FeC.

Surprisingly, FeC **2** treatment of A2780 cells leads to downregulation of expression β -actin (ACTB) as confirmed by RNA-Seq and validated by PCR (Figure 4B). We also observed that it is accompanied by the decrease of the level of intracellular β -actin protein (Figure 5F). Since β -actin is upregulated in the majority of cancer cells and is associated with invasiveness and metastasis of cancer,³⁸ these data could indicate that the FeC has a potential as an antimetastatic drug. We confirmed that it is indeed the case in two experiments. First, we observed that FeC **2** (3 μ M) substantially slows down migration of human lung cancer SK-MES-1 cells in wound healing assay (Figure S43, *SI*). Second, we found that the FeC exhibits antimetastatic activities *in vivo* as it is described in the next section.

Together with the ER stress and the associated oxidative stress, the effects of the FeC on cell cycle, DNA/RNA synthesis and cell proliferation induce cancer cell death (Table 1). We determined that the FeC **2** - induced death of A2780 and BL-2 cells occurs via apoptosis and necrosis (Figures S44-S48, *SI*). The cells can be only partially rescued by scavengers of ROS (N-acetylcysteine, NecroX5 methanesulfonate and ascorbic acid), whereas Ca^{2+} scavenger BAPTA and NOX2 inhibitor DPI exhibit no effect. These data indicate that the elevated ROS, but not Ca^{2+} and NOX2, play some role (downstream effect) in the anticancer activity of FeC **2**. Despite ROS is involved, according to our data discussed above the upstream factor of the activity of FeC **2** is the amplification of UPs, causing the ER stress and eventually the cell death in cancer cells.

Antitumor and antimetastatic activity of FeC 2 and its toxicity towards blood cells and bone marrow *in vivo*

Encouraged by excellent anticancer activity (Table 1) and cancer cell specificity (Figures 5C, S37, S39, S40B, *SI*) observed *in vitro*, we studied whether FeC **2** retains these favorable properties *in vivo*. First, we found that the toxicity of the FeC, injected intraperitoneally (i.p.) in C57/BL6 mice, is very low: the lethal dose (LD) is above 147 mg/kg (Table S16, *SI*). These data indicate that the FeC does not affect noncancerous cells *in vivo*, which is in agreement with the *in vitro* data obtained for SBLF9 cells (Figure 5C).

Next, we investigated the antitumor effect of the FeC in Nemeth-Kellner lymphoma (NK/Ly), which grow as solid tumors (sarcoma). This is a standard model for testing new chemotherapeutics in our laboratories.^{33,39} Untreated animals have a half-life of 32 days. For this therapy experiment we selected the dose of 12 mg/kg for a single injection. The compound was injected i.p. every second day for 10 times. This gives rise to the summary dose of 120

mg/kg, which is lower than the LD. The resulting from this experiment Kaplan-Meier (survival) plot is shown in Figure 6A. We observed that the mean survival time is statistically significantly

Figure 6. **A.** Survival of animals with NK/Ly sarcoma (**A**) and lymphoma (**B**) in control (DMSO) and FeC 2-treated groups. Experimental details are provided in the *SI*. **C.** Fluorescent microscopy of NK/Ly lymphoma cells grown in the abdominal cavity of mice isolated after 13 days treatment either with the carrier (DMSO) or FeC 2, and stained with TBMS-306 (20 nM, 10 min) (λ_{ex} = 630 nm; λ_{em} = 720 nm, Ch1). DIC= brightfield images. **D, E:** Antitumor (**C**) and antimetastatic (**D**) effects of FeC 2 in a murine Lewis lung carcinoma LLC1 model as observed on the 22 day of the experiment. An unpaired Student's t-test was performed for statistical analysis: * - $p < 0.05$; ** - $p < 0.01$; ns - $p \geq 0.05$. **F.** Monitoring of the number of white blood cells (WBC) and neutrophils (PMNs) in blood. The analysis was conducted on day 7. Paired t-test was conducted between days 0 and 7. *: $p < 0.05$; **: $p < 0.01$; ***: $p < 0.001$. The data for other blood and BM cells are provided in Figure S53, *SI*.

increased in the group treated with the FeC as compared to the group, which received only the carrier: from 32 to 75 days ($p < 0.0001$). On day 93, 3 survived mice in the treated group (27 % from the initial number of the animals: 11) were killed and dissected. We detected no signs of tumor indicating that these animals were completely cured (Figure S51, *SI*). This is an exciting result, which we have previously never observed for other Fe-containing drugs.^{33,39} Due to the excellent performance in the standard tumor model, we also have investigated its effects in the second, more challenging NK/Ly model, in which the cancer cells grow in the abdomen as ascites. This cancer is very aggressive and untreated animals have a half-life of only 18 days. We were pleased to observe the moderate activity of FeC 2. In particular, treatment with the FeC prolonged the life span of mice from 18 to 22 days ($p < 0.05$) (Figure 6B). On day 13 of this experiment, we collected ascites from the mice (0.3 mL, lymphoma tumor cells), treated them with a sensitive to MMP probe TBMS-306⁴⁰ (20 nM) and detected their fluorescence by fluorescence microscopy. We observed a strong signal in the control group and practically no signal in the FeC 2-treated group (Figure 6C). In the similar experiment, in which TBMS-306 was replaced with an MMP-independent Mit-probe TBMS-52⁴¹ (20 nM), no difference between

both groups was observed (Figure S49, SI). These data indicate that *in vivo* the FeC acts via the reduction of MMP, whereas the shape and size of Mit are not affected. Similar effects of the FeC on MMT of A2780 cells were also observed *in vitro* (Figures S25, S26, SI).

On day 23 of the experiment with the sarcoma model, one mouse from the control and one from the treated groups were killed and histology of tumor slices was conducted. We observed the increase in the number of cancer cells with fragmented nuclei in the treated group indicating that the FeC promotes cancer cell apoptosis *in vivo* (Figure S50, SI). As described above, the FeC also induces apoptosis of A2780 and BL-2 cells *in vitro* (Figures S44-49, SI). Thus, at least two effects of the FeC including the decrease of MMT and cell death via apoptosis are observed both *in vivo* and *in vitro*. These data may indicate that the modes of action of the FeC *in vitro* and *in vivo* are similar.

The FeC affects expression of β -actin and inhibits cell migration *in vitro* (Figure S43, SI). These preliminary studies justified the evaluation of antimetastatic properties of the FeC *in vivo*. We selected murine Lewis lung carcinoma LLC1 model, in which LLC1 cells grow as a primary tumor and form numerous metastases in lungs. The treatment included the i.p. injection of the FeC (48 mg/kg) twice per week for three weeks. On the 22nd day, tumor volume as well as the number and volume of metastases were evaluated (Figures 6D, E, S52, SI). We observed significant reduction of volume of the primary tumor ($p < 0.001$) and the number ($p < 0.001$) and volume ($p < 0.05$) of metastases in the treated group as compared to the control group.

Finally, we investigated the *in vivo* toxicity of the FeC towards a range of noncancerous cells at the therapeutically active dose of 12 mg/kg. They included white blood cells (WBC), red blood cells (RBC), platelets, polymorphonuclear neutrophils (PMNs), monocytes (MONO), lymphocytes (LYM) from blood. We also studied the effect of the FeC on BM cellularity and on the following BM cells: CD45+ cells, PMNs, MONO, B and T cells, LineageNEG Sca-1+ c-Kit+ cells and myeloid progenitors. As a positive control, we applied camptothecin (CPT), which exhibited strong toxicity towards the majority of these cells (Figure 6F, S53, SI). In contrast, no statistically significant toxicity of the FeC was observed (Figure 6F, S53, SI) that is in agreement with the high LD of this compound and its inability to generate mROS, NO and induce the ER stress (no sXBP1 upregulation) in representative normal SBLF9 cells as observed *in vitro* (Figures 5C, S37, S39, S40B, SI).

Conclusions

Known Fe²⁺-clathrochelates binding unfolded proteins are not cell membrane permeable and, therefore, do not exhibit anticancer activity. By the variation of their structure, we discovered FeC **2** containing a critical for the activity carboxylic acid moiety. Structurally, the FeC resembles fullerene C₆₀. However, in contrast to the latter carbon allotrope, it is more water soluble. The FeC can be considered as an inorganic mimic of C₆₀ suitable for medicinal applications. The FeC exhibits high to moderate anticancer activity towards a range of cancer cell lines derived from blood (HL-60, BL-2, Jurkat), ovary (A2780) and lungs (SK-MES1, LLC1). Furthermore, its activity is retained *in vivo* as confirmed for two Nemeth-Kellner lymphoma models and an LLC1 lung cancer model. In cells, the FeC acts as a monomer rather than an aggregate. It is stable in cells at the shorter incubation time (1h), but is partially (10 %) metabolized to its educt with glutathione at the longer incubation time (24 h). The latter metabolite does not contribute to the anticancer activity, since the initial cellular effects of the FeC, including the induction of the ER stress, appear very quickly at <10 min incubation time. The FeC is efficiently uptaken by cancer cells via the active mechanism mediated by clathrin and caveolin. In cells, it first induces the ER stress due to the accumulation of unfolded proteins

as evidenced by the activation of the protein ubiquitination pathway, which is reflected in upregulation of its genes and the increase of the amount of intracellular ubiquitinated proteins. The initial effect on the ER leads later on to the decrease of mitochondrial membrane potential, induction of oxidative stress including formation of mitochondrial ROS, upregulation of nitric oxide as well as growth arrest in the G1 phase and inhibition of DNA and RNA synthesis. All these factors cause cell apoptosis and partially necrosis. Interestingly, in contrast to cancer cells, the FeC does not affect the ROS, NO and sXBP1 levels in representative noncancerous SBLF9 cells indicating its cancer cell specificity. We further confirmed the cancer specificity of FeC **2** *in vivo*. In particular, it is reflected in very high lethal dose of 147 mg/kg of the FeC. Further, at its active dose of 12 mg/kg it does not induce any toxic effects on a range of cells in blood (white and red blood cells, platelets, neutrophils, monocytes, lymphocytes) and bone marrow (CD45+ cells, neutrophils, monocytes, B and T cells, lineageNEG Sca-1+ c-Kit+ cells and myeloid progenitors). Finally, the FeC exhibits significant antimetastatic activity in LLC1 lung cancer model. These data are in agreement with the FeC-mediated inhibition of β -actin expression and reduction of α -actin levels in cells observed *in vitro*.

In summary, the FeC is a metal-containing anticancer agent acting via the novel mechanism based on the intracellular unfolded protein amplification in the ER, and exhibiting high cancer cell specificity and, correspondingly, low toxicity as confirmed *in vitro* and *in vivo*.

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